

21ST Century Education: Classroom Management beyond Perspective

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ABSTRACT

Classroom management is one of the crucial factors that influence teaching and learning. This research has focused on a variety of the best strategies and practices of classroom management in a global approach. The findings of this study showed that good classroom management practices enable teachers and learners to meet on the prescribe desirable behavior of the learners. Further, different indicators have emerged as significant predictor of good classroom management practices. These include modeling appropriate behavior, offering praise to the learners, behavior management and establishing clear goals. These indicators elevate learner's positive behavior and engagement in the learning process. It also boosts learners' confidence and engagement in their learning. The finding of this study also showed that teachers with a different approach for classroom management will likely promote an effective learning environment that promotes globally competitive individuals.

KEYWORDS: Classroom Management, Behavior Management, Role model, Behavior

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INTRODUCTION

It is not undeniable that Classroom management is considered one of the most challenging issues in teaching and learning process. Creating an environment that promotes conducive for learning is probably the most important and one of the most difficult task a teacher faces (Canning, 2004).

However, Guido (2018) indicates that teachers overwhelmingly report lack of professional development support in improving classroom management. Shinn et al. (2002) noted that even though vast research literature has consistently emphasized the importance of classroom management knowledge for teachers beginning and experienced teachers tend to feel unprepared in management strategies: 'novice and experienced teachers consistently report that their training in classroom management was inadequate or impractical, and they require further preparation in this area' (Stough, 2006).

Moreover, Tartwijk and Hammemess (2011) stated that more attention for classroom management in teacher education is needed. The papers in this issue of Teaching Education help begin to deepen the conversation around the role of classroom management, by examining some of the ways in which classroom management is addressed in

teacher education in different countries. By sharing approaches to classroom management in teacher education that address classroom management in theoretical ways and that share data regarding its impact, the papers will begin to shed some light upon these issues. In turn, we hope to help advance conversations in the field of teacher education about the role of this important knowledge for pre-service teachers.

Classroom management is often an area of concern, especially for newer teachers. When classroom management breaks down, learning will suffer. The ability to manage the classroom naturally so that the managing of the classroom is not a focal point and does not take away from the instructional process is essential. Classroom Management is a means to an end, not the end in itself. Teachers, who focus only on managing the classroom, will often have a classroom that is devoid of excitement and energy. Teachers who focus only on instruction will often have a classroom that is interesting, exciting, and engaging, but one where students can easily be distracted from the job at hand and one where the noise can easily interfere with learning. It takes a balance between the management of students and their behavior, and sound engaging instruction for a teacher to be truly effective (London, 2015).

According to De Leon (2014) improving your classroom management means you are constantly working to create a learning environment in which all students feel safe and appropriately challenged. It implies the learning openings you give to understudies are composed and conveyed in manners that enable learners to succeed. Classroom management is a critical component of guaranteeing that all learners accomplish the learning goals and objectives of the school.

Furthermore, Heather (2018) stated that effective classroom management strategies involve organization, fostering good working relationships, as well as a disciplined yet personable attitude. Deciding which techniques to use can nonetheless be difficult, as every student and class is unique. Establishing a distinct classroom routine with your students helps them know exactly what to expect. The ability to anticipate the structure of your lessons and the expectations you hold can cultivate a productive working atmosphere.

Based on the articles WeareTeachersStaff (2019) Classroom management can be learned these includes when you watch a teacher with great classroom management techniques, it can feel like magic. The truth is that classroom management can be learned. Reading about classroom management, asking other teachers what they do, and even talking with your principal about what they have observed can help.

Classroom management in relation to teachers’ phases of development

According to London (2015) there are three phases of management that are essential in building the foundation for success in teachers. They are Classroom Management, Behavior Management, and Instructional Management. These three phases are so interrelated that a failure or weakness in one of them can significantly impact the other two. Principals need to look closely at all three especially in cases where a teacher is struggling, to help that teacher remediate and maintain student academic performance in that classroom. With the average age and experience levels of the teaching force continuing to decrease, principals must be prepared to work with those teachers in their buildings to maximize their performance and as a result student progress.

Classroom and Behavior Management

Many teachers assume that classroom management and behavior management are the same. While these two concepts are closely related, they are not the same. Classroom management is comprised in great part with the active planning a teacher does to create the classroom climate and a set of procedures that will allow students to function with a minimum of uncertainty. Classroom management is the handling of the routine, but important tasks that teachers are responsible for with a minimum of lost instructional time these includes those activities, routines and procedures that teachers establish and engage in to manage the instructional environment, establish a climate for learning and maximize the use of time for instruction. Classroom Management is a series of decisions designed to help teachers smoothly and efficiently handle routine tasks, and establish routines and procedures so that students know what to do and how to do it, and establishes the expectations for students and the teacher alike. These routines and procedures allow students to be able to

anticipate what their teacher wants from them in the way of behavior. The students need to be able to anticipate what the teacher wants from them via the routines and procedures established for the classroom. When students do not know what to anticipate in a classroom their insecurity becomes heightened and that often results in behavior that does not meet the teacher’s expectations. Classroom management includes the establishment of behavioral expectations and consequences for students failing to meet those expectations. Behavior management is what the teacher does to remediate any students not meeting expectations so that they will be more likely to meet those expectations in the future, these are the activities that teachers engage in after a student or students have failed to meet the established expectations and the classroom environment has been disrupted impacting student learning. Managing student behavior is what the teacher does after the expectations have been established to ensure the environment stays productive and students know the routines and procedures. Behavior management is what the teacher does when despite having established the routines and expectations for an effective classroom, a student or students disrupt the learning process (London 2015).

Objective of the Study

Although related studies and research findings have indicated the importance of classroom management in the teaching and learning process, but still this issues have not prioritizes and somewhat ignored. Reinforcing the role of classroom management is a need to improve the quality and stability of the learning of the learners. Hence, this research would find out what are the best strategies and practices of classroom management in a global approach.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Given the importance of classroom management in the school, the following best practices were examined and determined in order to meet the needs of the teachers and learners in the learning process. Teachers utilize this strategies to create an environment that reflect quality and effective learning environment.

Modeling an Ideal Behavior

Modeling positive behavior helps create a positive environment where students feel safe and cared for and where they can develop behavioral skills.

Modeling of Appropriate Behavior

Figure1.

The above figure indicates that modeling of appropriate teachers’ behavior can increase the likelihood of the learners’ good behavior inside the classroom. The use of polite language, maintain eye contact, keep phones in your pockets and raise concerns about one another statement in a respectful manner have found out that these indicators

influence the behavior of the students. According to Nucaro (2017) the use of compassionate and straightforward language allows students to build trust in their teachers and fosters an environment of growth. Students who are spoken to directly and honestly are more likely to feel respected and safe, while also receiving the support they need to be successful both academically and behaviorally.

Moreover, Barati (2015) stated that by having a good relationship with students, teachers can offer to students chances to be motivated and feel engaged in the learning process. Students will be engaged actively. The use of the eyes to convey messages. For both the teacher and the learner, the eyes are a powerful tool around the teaching and learning environment. Eye contact produces a powerful, subconscious sense of connection that extends even to drawn or photographed eyes. Because it is connected with humans' earliest survival patterns. Children who could attract and maintain eye contact, and therefore increase attention, had the best chance of being fed and cared for.

Moreover, Lynch (2017) noted that the best way to create a set of rules when it comes to cell phone usage is to do it together with the students. Include a clear list of times that it is and isn't appropriate to be using your phone in class. It's also important to agree on and clearly lay out the consequences of breaking the rules. You can even write up a contract or agreement laying out all of the expectations and effects you agreed upon as a class, and have them read it over and sign it. This way students know what to expect, and there are no surprises when they're caught using their smart phones. Meador (2019) noted that Your students will never respect you if you do not respect them. You should never yell, use sarcasm, single a student out, or attempt to embarrass them. Those things will lead to a loss of respect from the entire class. Teachers should handle situations professionally. You should deal with problems individually, in a respectful, yet direct and authoritative manner. Teachers must treat each student the same. You cannot play favorites. The same set of rules must apply to all students. It is also vital that a teacher is fair and consistent when dealing with students. To sum-up the data shows that modeling appropriate behavior will boost learners understanding on the expected behavior that they need to perform. Teachers must exercise these practices to bring positive change in the classroom that enable learners to join and bring out the modeled positive behavior.

Offer Praise

Offering praise for students' work and efforts can alter this mindset so that students can begin to view their own intelligence as something that can be developed. This mindset of developing intelligence will increase students' ability to "bounce back" in the face of academic setbacks and other difficulties.

Figure2.

As shown in figure 2, the data revealed that teachers, who often give praise to their learners have elevated the students self confidence and bring positive behavior in the school. According to Morin (2014) praise is one of the simplest and most powerful tools to engage and motivate your students. When used effectively, praise can turn around behavior challenges and improve students' attitudes about learning. Students who learn and think differently often receive negative feedback as a result of their struggles. That makes meaningful and appropriate praise even more important. Feedback is an essential part of effective learning. It helps students understand the subject being studied and gives them clear guidance on how to improve their learning. Bellon *et al.* state academic feedback is more strongly and consistently related to achievement than any other teaching behavior this relationship is consistent regardless of grade, socioeconomic status, race, or school setting. Feedback can improve a student's confidence, self-awareness and enthusiasm for learning. Effective feedback during the first year in university can aid the transition to higher education and may support student retention. Providing students engage with feedback, it should enhance learning and improve assessment performance. Therefore, it is safe to say that a teacher who often gives praise to the learners have boost the learner's effort and confidence to continue striving hard and participate in the teaching and learning process. Hence, teachers are encouraged to give praise to the learners to boost their confidence and learning.

Behavior Management

Behavior management refers to a class of therapeutic techniques for altering behavior by changing one or more aspects of an individual's environment. The aspects that are changed are those believed to contribute most significantly to the occurrence or maintenance of behaviors that are problematic for the individual himself/herself or for other individuals in the environment.

Figure3.

In terms of classroom management, the data revealed that reinforcement was the most employed behavior management strategies of the teachers the same with the learners, to lessen the occurrence of undesirable behavior of the learners. According to Prince (2013) reinforcement is used to help increase the probability that a specific behavior will occur in the future by delivering or removing a stimulus immediately after a behavior and if done correctly, results in a behavior occurring more frequently in the future. Moreover, punishment was not the most effective behavior management strategy when dealing with learners behavior. According to Horwitz (2015) punishment may teach a kid

that something is unpleasant, but it does not teach the kid what is desirable. Teaching desirable behavior should focus on reinforcing what is desirable and not punishing what is undesirable. While reinforcement can increase behaviors that we want to train, punishment can only decrease behaviors that we want to stop. Furthermore, along with the findings, it shows that modeling was second most employed behavior management strategy of the teachers, this entails that after reinforcement, the teachers modeled the appropriate behavior to really understand the learners on how to be a responsible learners. According to Inome (2016) modelling behaviors is specific direct instruction of behaviors that students need to be learning. Modeling behaviors can be for behavior in the classroom, social environments and other school settings such as the playground or cafeteria. With modeling, the teacher typically identifies and introduces the behavior that he/she is planning to model and why it is important. Hence, Modeling is one of the most important ways to teach the behaviors we want. It's a fact that as teachers, we often expect learners to demonstrate exemplary behavior, then during class hours they show undesirable behavior, that is why it is very important to model on how to be a responsible learners by showing them on how to do that.

Establish Clear Goals

Establishing and communicating learning goals at the beginning of a unit of instruction or at the beginning of the school year has found that it could enhance communication between teachers and students.

Figure 4.

Figure 4 shows the importance of establishing clear goals towards positive learning environment in the classroom. Unsurprisingly, indicators that refers to including the learners in establishing guidelines is also a big factor in creating a safe and conducive learning environment. According to Harmon (2017) Creating expectations with students is an empowering activity to help build the community and culture of the art room. Allowing students to take ownership over their environment shows them you value their thoughts. Further, Giving students a say will allow them to feel valued. As they contribute to the classroom expectations, they are more likely to follow them. They also will be able to use their critical thinking skills as they develop ideas to share with the class. It is beneficial to have student investment to promote a positive and safe learning environment.

Conclusion

This research study explores classroom management approaches in global perspective and good practices. The findings of this study showed that good classroom management practices enable teachers and learners meet on the prescribe desirable behavior of the learners. Further, different indicators have emerged as significant predictor of good classroom management practices. These includes modeling appropriate behavior, offering praise to the learners, behavior management and establishing clear goals. These indicators elevate the learners positive behavior and engagement in the learning process. It also boost learners confidence and engagement in their learning. The finding on this study also showed that teacher with different approach for classroom management will likely promote effective learning environment that promote globally competitive individual.

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